

THE ROLE OF NEUROGRAPHY IN ART THERAPY

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Abstract. *This article presents an opinion about art therapy and its types, neurography and the history of its development.*

Keywords: *art therapy, neurography, mental state, types of art therapy, therapy, emotional state.*

Introduction (Introduction). Art therapy (English: art — "art" + therapy- treatment) is one of the areas of psychotherapy and psychological correction based on the use of art and creativity. In the narrow sense of the word, art therapy usually refers to visual art therapy aimed at influencing the psycho-emotional state of the client.

The main goal of art therapy is to harmonize the state of mind through the development of self-expression and self-awareness. The importance of using art for therapeutic purposes is the symbolic expression of various emotions: love, hate, sadness, anger, fear, joy, etc. and can be used for learning.. The art therapy technique is based on the conclusion that the content of a person's inner "I" is reflected in the visual images he draws or sculpts, and the state of the psyche changes.

Types of art therapy

Strictly speaking, art therapy is drawing therapy based on visual arts (isotherapy). Popular for identifying and correcting neurotic and psychosomatic disorders among children and adolescents with learning and social adjustment difficulties. This process represents the emotional state of the person who painted.

Bibliotherapy (including fairy tale therapy) is the creative reading or creation of artistic compositions and works of art.

Music therapy

Drama therapy

Dance therapy

Doll therapy

Sand therapy

Sculpture therapy

Phototherapy

Play therapy

Therapy using metaphorical associative maps.[1]

Difficulties in emotional development, stress, depression, low mood, emotional instability, impulsivity of emotional reactions, emotional rejection of other people, feelings of loneliness, interpersonal conflicts, dissatisfaction with family relationships, increased anxiety, fear, phobia, negative "self-concept", self in cases of low evaluation, it is appropriate to use art therapy. The role of music, colors, paintings, and dances in human life is very incomparable. art. The symbol of cultural recreation is directly music and art. For this reason, we believe that it is permissible to use art as therapy instead of therapy.

In modern psychology, one of the types of Art therapy is being formed on the basis of Isotherapy, "Neurographics". "Neuro" - brain, "graphics" - I write, that is, I write the mind.

Neurographics is a visual way of working with problems and an effective exercise to change your life for the better. It was developed by artist and psychologist Pavel Piskarev in 2014. Neurographics combines a set of psychological approaches with several graphic imaging techniques. At first glance, such graphs seem abstract, but their basis is not only emotional - they are neurological; Drawing neuroscience is directly related to depicting reality.[2]

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review).

Neurographics is an opportunity to unlock your potential

The purpose of neurographic imaging is to describe unconscious fears, beliefs, tensions, and experiences of a person's past and soul's previous life. Limitations that hinder the development of the individual rise to the level of consciousness, where they can be transformed into ideas that give positive results. This practice allows you to make a decision, get an answer to a question, solve a problem and make a wish come true.

A popular way to make wishes come true is to create a "wish card" - a collage of ready-made images that represent a dream. Those who know that a wish will come true if you visualize it clearly use this method. The easiest way to imagine what you want is to create a visual image of it.

The secret of the neurological method of visualization of desires lies in the specific features of the human psyche, which consists of images obtained through visual perception. During a neurological session, a person's psychological experience is realized, everything we do, everything we think, everything we want rises to the level of consciousness.

A person feels a sense of confidence and trust that his desire has come true. This is partly because he has already put his wishes on paper. After some time, a person stops thinking about this topic, after which his wish will come true. Experts from many countries have recognized neurological imaging as the best solution to goals and tasks in human life.

Neurographics is a way to control your life by painting. You can draw anything, absolutely anything.

The most interesting thing is that through neurographics we can work with negative emotions, release pent-up emotions, avoid stress, self-destructive confessions, destructive subconscious programs and other such harmful situations. we can be

Neurographics teach us how to think positively. Through positive thinking, we can achieve what we want, saturate ourselves with energy, "attract" people, events, pleasant situations to us, create new, happy scenarios. Most importantly, drawing neurographics is very easy, fun, interesting and fun!

Research methodology (Research Methodology).

It is very difficult to change behavior by will. We need a language that is understandable to the brain and forms new neural connections. Currently, the most effective way to do this is neurography. Through the process familiar to everyone from childhood - drawing expresses thoughts, feelings. As a result, restrictions are removed and beliefs change, the perception of the problem and the attitude towards it change. With this, we find new solutions, ways of doing things and opportunities. We can say that neurography is a transition to the desired reality.

Neurography is used for the following purposes:

- not to hide feelings, open anger, fear, anxiety, turn them into positive emotions;
- elimination of internal conflicts that lead to the development of psychosomatic diseases;

- development of a non-standard approach to solving problems in the professional and financial sphere, career and business;
- planning of events, change for the better;
- to improve relations with relatives, colleagues, friends.

Neurography teaches how to change a person's attitude to situations, people, life, and to be completely independent from the fluctuations of the outside world.

Analysis and results (Analysis and results).

All you need for neurography is a sheet of paper, a pencil and markers. And some free time. It is important to pay attention to your feelings when working.

1. We pronounce a topic that causes negative emotions, internal contradictions, anxiety, fear, internal rejection. At the same time, it is desirable to name the feelings that appear at this stage, to understand the level of internal tension and the amount of growing energy.

2. We express emotions in the form of a neurographic line or number. During the drawing process, the entire sheet is filled with lines that can overlap, touch or merge. At the same time, it is necessary to focus not on the beauty of the line, but on the drawing process itself.

3. We check and correct the obtained lines and their intersection forms. Sharp corners and intersecting lines in the picture indicate the presence of internal conflicts. To get rid of them, you need to wash them. There is no need to explain the parts of the picture. At this stage there is a change in reality and the removal of psychological limitations. In the process of implementation, it is important to observe how the feelings and emotions that appeared at the first stage have changed.

4. We combine separate sections of the drawing into single shapes by coloring them with a marker or colored pencil. The number of plots, the color of the lines and the filling of the space between them are not important. This work helps to reduce internal tension, reduce internal conflict, release positive energy that helps to solve the problem.

5. We define and draw the main lines of the picture. Here comes getting rid of the problem or its solution that seemed insurmountable in the first step.

6. Assess changes in emotional state. If one feels it

1. the stage of lightness and freedom, then the goal is reached. If the feeling of inner peace and harmony has not come, then you need to draw many circles of different sizes on all the numbers and lines. This helps to reduce the level of internal tension caused by the topic announced in the first step.

Many people who have never painted before, regardless of their main occupation, easily become addicted to neurography.

Conclusions and recommendations (Conclusion/Recommendations).

Advantages of neurography

- Availability. Neurography does not require special conditions, only silence to pay attention to the process.
- Simplicity. Special drawing skills are not needed, as simple shapes are used:
 - circle, triangle and square. The main thing is to express feelings, problems and situations on paper.
- Speed. Simple requests can be processed in a few hours.

Disadvantages of neurography

Despite the universality of the method, there are some points to consider in neurography.

We cannot always deal with feelings and emotions alone. Often you need someone to ask the questions that we avoid and are afraid to truly assess the situation. Therefore, not all requests can be drawn independently. Choose certified neuroscience instructors to accompany you.

Difficulty dealing with deeply negative situations. For such cases, a longer time and an experienced teacher are required.

Neurography, like no other method, helps to realize one's potential, fulfill desires in a simple and effective way.

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